

FORMATION AND STUDY OF STATIC AND DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTRONICALLY CONTROLLED DIESEL ENGINE

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Manufacturing companies of electronic control systems of diesel engines protect access to a program operation algorithm of the regulator that makes impossible adjustments and settings of its work, for example, at re-equipment or operational development of a new diesel engine. Therefore it is important to acknowledge the solution of the scientific and technical problem of an effective and reliable system creation of electronic control of diesel fuel supply with an open program algorithm of its work. During current research settlement and experimental studies of a diesel engine supplied with a system of electronic control of a crankshaft rotation frequency developed by the authors showed rather high adequacy in results. The dynamic mathematical model of the research single-cylinder diesel engine supplied with the electronic regulator of rotation frequency was developed and verified.

Keywords: *diesel engine, electronic regulator, mathematical modeling, characteristics*

1. INTRODUCTION

At the moment leading countries continue to improve motor vehicles in order to achieve new qualities for consumers, e.g., improved controllability, ergonomics, fuel efficiency, reduction of harmful emissions into the atmosphere, improvement safety, comfort, noise level, vibration, etc. This primarily concerns the improvement of the internal combustion engine (ICE), especially diesel engines.

It is known that the diesel engine works in the wide range of the load, high-speed and thermal modes. At the same time, reduction of harmful emissions, fuel consumption, noise and vibration of the engine is promoted by such organization of management process of this object which provides the most high-quality transitional processes on all field of its possible operating modes. It is indisputable that this optimization is impossible without realization of special algorithms by electronic control systems.

However, the cost of electronic systems of regulation remains rather high, and their service and repair demands existence of expensive and difficult equipment, as also highly skilled personnel. Besides, manufacturing companies of such systems protect access to a program operation algorithm of regulator that makes impossible adjustments and settings of its work, for example, at re-equipment or operational development of a new diesel engine.

The scientific publications devoted to development and research of algorithms of electronic control systems of engines practically are absent, and those which are known differ in laconicism of material supply.

For example, in publications [1, 2] there is information about the practical creation of electronic control systems for diesel engines, where fuel supply is controlled not by the rail of fuel pump, but by the high-pressure bleed solenoid valve. In these publications are described such themes as the design, schemes, results of experimental studies and mathematical modeling, but the description of the algorithms is not disclosed by the authors. In addition, the features of diesel locomotive operation do not allow transferring the control algorithm on engines for land transport or special equipment.

Recently there was a set of the scientific publications describing the research works devoted to introduction of electronic control by the engine test bench [3, 4]. The purpose of these works is reproduction of engine transient test cycles of the engine for definition of their ecological indicators. However, here, though originally, but the problem of management is solved by absolutely other object – the loading device.

There are also publications on the development of control algorithms for individual systems of an internal combustion engine - a fuel pressure accumulator [5], an air supply system [6], an exhaust gas recirculation system [7], etc., that also does not relate directly to the regulation system of the engine high-speed mode.

The publication [8] is the most appropriate material on the formulation of the problem and the methods. Authors of this research have used a control algorithm based on the interpolation of the static characteristics of the regulator stored in the controller in tabular form. This approach has some disadvantages because such organization of calculations introduces additional load on the central processor of the controller and leads to an increase in the intrinsic time (inertia) of the electronic regulator.

Therefore it is important to acknowledge the solution of the scientific and technical problem on creation of an effective and reliable system of electronic control of diesel fuel supply with an open program algorithm of its work.

The purpose of this article is settlement and experimental studies of a diesel engine supplied with a system of electronic control of rotation frequency of a crankshaft developed by the authors to confirm its reliable performance and efficiency.

2. THE THEORETICAL PART NO.1. BASICS OF THE ALGORITHMIZATION OF THE ELECTRONIC ALL-MODE DIESEL REGULATOR

For the synthesis of the electronic control algorithm for the rail of a high-pressure fuel pump (HPFP) a scientific approach has been applied based on the analogy with the operation of an all-mode mechanical spring-lever speed controller of direct action. Mechanical all-mode regulators of diesel engines provide accepted (but, not always optimum) operational regulatory characteristics and also are rather reliable units.

Let's consider operation of such mechanical all-mode regulator with a variable tightening of a spring. Its schematic diagram is provided on Fig. 1. To this scheme there corresponds the structural logic diagram (Fig. 2) which is constructed

on the basis of replacement of physical processes (linear movements of links or operating forces) with information ones. For example, movement of the coupling of a sensitive element under the influence of inertia force of the rotating mass of freights can be presented as a certain algorithm of measurement of rotation speed, and spring tightening force – as an algorithm of processing of change of the main external influence. From this point of view, the lever of the regulator can be presented how a certain calculator whose equilibrium position unambiguously defines value of an output signal of movement of a rail of HPFP, (Hp).

Fig. 1. The all-mode regulator with a variable tightening of a spring. Schematic diagram

Fig. 2. Scheme of information analogy of operation of the all-mode regulator

Then a condition of static balance of the all-mode regulator with a variable tightening of a spring is possible to describe by mathematical equality:

$$E \cdot (b + c) = D \cdot c. \quad (1)$$

Here E is a conditional restoring force which is similar to regulator spring tightening force. This force consists of force of a preliminary tightening of a spring (E_0) and its current deformations brought to the lever connected with the movement of a control lever (X) and a rail of HPFP (Hp):

$$E = E_0 + C \cdot \bar{X} \cdot (X_{\max} - X_{\min}) \frac{e}{d + e} - C \cdot \bar{Hp} \cdot (Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min}) \frac{b + c}{a + b + c}, \quad (2)$$

where C – virtual coefficient of rigidity of a spring, N/m. *With line in this formula and further relative sizes are designated.*

The conditional supporting force $D = f(\omega)$ – in fact, is a measuring instrument of rotation speed. Let's assume that it comply with linear dependence. Then:

$$D = K \cdot \bar{\omega} \cdot (\omega_{\max} - \omega_{\min}) = K \frac{\pi}{30} \bar{n} \cdot (n_{\max} - n_{\min}). \quad (3)$$

In this formula the constant coefficient of proportionality K conditionally has dimension of Ns (an analog of inertial coefficient of the mechanical regulator).

After substitution of expressions (2) and (3) in the initial equation (1) and their simple transformation it is possible to come to the general equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_0}{C(Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min})} \cdot \frac{a+b+c}{b+c} + \frac{X_{\max} - X_{\min}}{Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min}} \cdot \frac{e(a+b+c)}{(d+e)(b+c)} \cdot \bar{X} - \bar{Hp} = \\ = \frac{\pi}{30} \cdot \frac{K(n_{\max} - n_{\min})}{C(Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min})} \cdot \frac{c(a+b+c)}{(b+c)^2} \bar{n}. \end{aligned}$$

It is visible that at this equation there are constants which we will designate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 = \frac{E_0}{C(Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min})} \cdot \frac{a+b+c}{b+c}, \quad A = \frac{X_{\max} - X_{\min}}{Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min}} \cdot \frac{e(a+b+c)}{(d+e)(b+c)}, \\ B = \frac{\pi}{30} \frac{K(n_{\max} - n_{\min})}{C(Hp_{\max} - Hp_{\min})} \cdot \frac{c(a+b+c)}{(b+c)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Then we have record of the equation (1) in look:

$$\bar{Hp} = A_1 + A \cdot \bar{X} - B \cdot \bar{n}. \quad (4)$$

The received equation (4) is a required algorithm of the electronic regulator operation. Using it is possible to calculate static characteristics of the regulator in the form of dependence $\bar{Hp} = f(\bar{X}, \bar{n})$, and selection of values of coefficients of A_1 , A and B – set their required look. The following values of coefficients were accepted: $A_1 = 0.58$, $A = 1.22$ and $B = 1$.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PART NO. 1. IMPLEMENTATION OF A CONTROL SYSTEM AT THE RESEARCH MOTOR BENCH

For check of operability of the described operation algorithm of the electronic regulator of a crankshaft rotation frequency, engine testing studies were realized. The engine (the cylinder sizes: diameter of 120 mm, a piston stroke of 140 mm) used, which was mounted on the laboratory test bench. This engine is the single-cylinder diesel with power up to 30 kW with a crankshaft rotation frequency from 700 to 1400 min⁻¹. Diesel engine test bench differs in the following design features:

- Injection of fuel in a cylinder is carried out by the high pressure fuel feeding system with the individual fuel pump (Unit Pump System).
- The engine lubrication system autonomous.

- The cooling system – liquid, autonomous, with separate streams of cooling liquid in the block and a head of a cylinder.
- Engine start is carried out by means of the electric load device which is a part of the test bench.
- The engine has the mechanism of equilibration of inertia forces like *Lanchester*.
- In a head of a cylinder the gas channel for installation of the indication sensor is realized.

Besides, the test bench is equipped with all necessary devices and sensors for carrying out measurements of the current operation parameters of the engine.

The function chart of the developed electronic system of automatic control (SAC) of the diesel is shown in Fig. 3. As it is seen from the drawing, external and internal influences of such SAC are: $X(t)$ – the current position of governing body of the engine, $n(t)$ – the current rotation frequency of a crankshaft of the engine, H_p – position of governing body of fuel feeding (rail of HPFP), B_c – cyclic supply of fuel by HPFP and $M_c(t)$ – the loading resistance moment. The letter t designate the current time.

Fig. 3. Function chart of the electronic regulator of crankshaft rotation frequency

The main components of the developed system of the electronic regulator are: ECU on *ATmega328* microcontroller; actuator; position sensors of a pedal of an accelerator, the «Start» and «Auto» buttons which are intended for initialization, according to the engine starting modes and PID regulation. As the actuator for the drive of a rail of the fuel pump there was used step actuator developed by company «DigasGroup» (Latvia).

The accelerator pedal sensor is intended for registration of movement of a control lever and transmits the corresponding signal to ECU.

Crankshaft rotation frequency calculates by time of the period of signal of the inductive sensor installed opposite to a flywheel on which the magnetic plate is located.

The microcontroller processes primary received information from sensors, the “Start” and “Auto” buttons and realizes the program control algorithm putted in it. By results of processing of these signals the microcontroller reacts via the

actuator. Contact of the microcontroller with the actuator is realized through the protocol of data transmission MAX-485.

ECU has the converter of interfaces USB-UART using which connection to the personal computer for its programming is carried out.

As the interface 16 symbolical liquid crystal indicator is used on which the current information is transmitted: relative provision of a rail of the fuel pump and control lever, operating mode of the regulator, etc. Electronic regulator does not demand change of a design of the fuel pump, it is flexible and universal in regulation, can be installed on various types of diesel engines.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PART NO. 2. STATIC AND DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DIESEL

The carried-out motor tests of a control system on the research diesel showed that at introduction of electronic regulation on the equilibrium modes stability of crankshaft rotation frequency considerably increases (to $\Delta n = \pm 2 \text{ min}^{-1}$) irrespective of fuel quality, technical condition of the engine, environmental conditions and other external factors.

The program of the carried-out tests in the form of a set of pairs of setting regime parameters were following: "relative position of governing body of X – Mc loading resistance moment size" and the measured indicators corresponding to them: crankshaft rotation frequencies n , the current relative provision of a rail of HPFP Hp and mass hour fuel consumption.

The results received during tests allowed:

1. Experimentally confirm a type of static characteristic of the electronic regulator.
2. Define and visualize regulatory characteristics of the diesel (provided on Fig. 4) – dependence of value of relative effective torque \overline{Me} of the crankshaft rotation frequency n at various constant provisions of governing body of X.

Fig. 4. Regulatory characteristics of the diesel engine

3. Define and visualize static characteristic of HPFP of the research diesel engine (provided on Fig. 5) – dependence of relative value of its volume cyclic supply of fuel on the rotation frequency of crankshaft n at various

constant provisions of governing body of X.

Fig. 5. Static characteristic of HPFP with the regulator

4. Synthesize a basic matrix of fuel feeding of $Bc = f(n, X)$ for the current diesel which is necessary for creation of more complex system of management on the basis of predictive model (*Model Predictive Control*). This matrix is received by method of interpolation-extrapolation of data in 22 separate experimental points. Graphically this matrix is presented in the surface form in Fig. 6. In the same place values of the experimental data, which formed a basis for synthesis of the table, are showed.

Fig. 6. The synthesized basic table of fuel feeding with experimental points (+)

Apparently from the provided drawings, the results received during the experiment do not contradict to the standard requirements of regulation systems of

diesel engines of different functions, especially in transport. Besides, the carried tests of the engine showed that use of the offered electronic regulator allowed to reduce time of transition processes between the required set modes.

Also, for development and verification of dynamic mathematical model of the studied diesel control system, there were received records of a temporary track of the crankshaft current speed at the determined change of position of governing body of the engine. Example is given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Dynamic characteristics and results of mathematical modeling of an electronic system of regulation: ---- calculation; — experiment

5. THEORETICAL PART NO. 2. DESCRIPTION AND VERIFICATION OF MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF DYNAMICS OF A CONTROL SYSTEM

The calculation scheme of mathematical model of the developed electronic control system is provided on Fig. 8. On this scheme in the form of internal information communications the following sizes used as system coordinates are designated: ΔHp – the rejection of the provision of a rail of HPFP demanded for achievement of the equilibrium mode; $\Delta Hp'$ – the valid deviation of a rail of HPFP from equilibrium situation; $\Delta \omega$ – the current deviation from equilibrium value of angular speed of a crankshaft; ω_0 – value of angular speed of the set equilibrium mode; n – absolute value of rotation frequency of the engine; X – position of governing body of the engine.

For the description of the movement of a crankshaft of the engine we will use the known differential equation

$$J \frac{d\omega}{dt} = Me - Mc \cdot \quad (5)$$

Fig. 8. Calculation scheme of mathematical model

Assuming that the effective torque of the engine M_e is linearly proportional to the size of cyclic supply of fuel Bc (that is fair for naturally aspirated engine), which unambiguously is determined by the current valid position of a rail of HPFP Hp' .

$$M_e = f(Bc) = f(Hp') = A_A \cdot Hp'.$$

Also we will consider that the loading resistance moment M_c linearly depends on the angular crankshaft rotation speed.

$$M_c = f(\omega) = B_B \cdot \omega.$$

Here A_A, B_B – constant coefficients of proportionality.

The equation (5) taking into account a small deviation from the equilibrium mode Δ , registers as follows:

$$J \frac{d(\omega_0 + \Delta\omega)}{dt} = A_A \cdot (Hp'_0 + \Delta Hp') - B_B \cdot (\omega_0 + \Delta\omega).$$

Considering a preliminary condition of the steady, equilibrium mode $M_e(Hp'_0) = M_c(\omega_0)$, also zero derivative of constants, it can be simplified and given to the normalized look:

$$J \frac{d\Delta\omega}{dt} = A_A \cdot \Delta Hp' - B_B \cdot \Delta\omega. \quad (6)$$

The received equation (6) is the main settlement equation of mathematical model. Its numerical decision relatively $\Delta\omega$ will allow to define the current deviation of rotation frequency from its equilibrium value n_0 :

$$\Delta n = 9,549 \cdot \Delta\omega.$$

Then the absolute value of the current frequency of rotation will be $n = n_0 + \Delta n$.

The required value of equilibrium provision of a rail of HPFP (mathematical description of work of an algorithm of ECU) for the current cycle is calculated on a formula (4) taking into account that $Hp = Hp_0 + \Delta Hp$, where $\Delta Hp = A_1 + A \cdot X - B \cdot n - Hp_0$.

Writing up the differential equation of the movement of a rail of HPFP it is accepted that it is without inertial part, but its movement is realized to constant

relative linear speed $C = \frac{d\Delta Hp'}{dt} = 0,0415 \text{ s}^{-1}$. At the same time, its movement continuously continues before achievement of the set equilibrium situation $Hp = Hp_0 + \Delta Hp$ and takes time $\Delta t_K = \frac{\Delta Hp}{C}$. Therefore, change of the valid rejection of the position of a rail of HPFP in time can be described by the integrated equation $\Delta Hp' = C \int_{t_0}^{t_0 + \frac{\Delta Hp}{C}} dt$.

The general algorithm of creation of calculations for the described mathematical model has the following sequence.

1. The current time interval for numerical integration on i-th step:

$$\Delta t_i = 120/n_{i-1}.$$

2. The current required rejection of the provision of a rail of HPFP for achievement of the equilibrium mode:

$$\Delta Hp_i = A_1 + A \cdot X_i - B \cdot n_{i-1} - Hp_0.$$

3. The current valid rejection of the provision of a rail of HPFP in each timepoint $t_i = t_{i-1} + \Delta t_i$ till moment $t_K = t_0 + \Delta t_K$:

$$\Delta Hp'_i = C(t_i - t_0).$$

4. Current deviation of crankshaft angular speed:

$$\Delta \omega_i = \frac{1}{J} (A_A \cdot \Delta Hp'_i - B_B \cdot \Delta \omega_{i-1}) \Delta t_i + \Delta \omega_{i-1}.$$

5. Current value of rotation frequency of the engine:

$$n_i = n_0 + \frac{30}{\pi} \Delta \omega_i.$$

After verification of the mathematical model consisting in selection of values of the mass moment of inertia of mobile parts of engine J and coefficients of proportionality A_A, B_B in equation (6), comparative calculation for the received experimentally temporary track of the current speed of a crankshaft $n(t)$ at the determined change of position of governing body of the engine $X(t)$ is carried out. Its results are showed on the experimental graph (Fig. 7). At the same time values $J = 30 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$ were accepted (used single-cylinder engine has a massive flywheel), $A_A = 1375 \text{ Nm}$, $B_B = 0.05 \text{ Nm}$.

As it is seen from the drawing, the model rather adequately repeats an experimental track that validates the developed calculation procedure and allows to use this mathematical model as the tool for carrying out further settlement researches.

6. CONCLUSIONS

As a result of performance of this research work the following main results were received.

1. Theoretical justification of synthesis of a program operation algorithm of the electronic regulator of diesel engine rotation frequency is realized.
2. The system of electronic all-mode regulation of crankshaft rotation frequency of the diesel engine is developed and implemented on the motor

research bench.

3. The operability of the developed electronic regulation system is completely confirmed by research studies of additional device. During tests static and dynamic characteristics of this system are received.
4. The dynamic mathematical model of the research single-cylinder diesel engine supplied with the electronic regulator of rotation frequency is developed and verified. Results of calculation with the use of this mathematical model have showed its rather high adequacy.
5. For the studied diesel the basic matrix of fuel feeding $Bc = f(n, X)$ is synthesized, necessary for creation of a control system on the basis of predictive model.

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ELEKTRONISKI VADĀMA DĪZEĻMOTORA STATISKO UN DINAMISKO RAKSTURLĪKŅU IZVEIDE UN IZPĒTE

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Kopsavilkums

Dīzeļmotoru elektronisko vadības sistēmu ražojošās kompānijas aizsargā piekļuvi regulatoru algoritmu darbības programmām, kas padara praktiski neiespējamu to darbības korekciju un iestatījumu maiņu, piemēram, jauna dīzeļmotora pārbūves vai uzlabošanas gadījumos. Tāpēc ir svarīgi atzīmēt zinātniski-tehniskos šādu problēmu risinājumus, kas saistīti ar efektīvu un uzticamu sistēmu izveidi dīzeļdegvielas padeves sistēmas kontrolei ar atvērtās darba programmas algoritmu. Teorētiskajos un eksperimentālajos pētījumos par autoru izveidoto dīzeļmotora kloķvārpstas apgriezienu elektroniskās kontroles sistēmu tika konstatēta iegūto rezultātu zināma līdzība. Pētījumu gaitā tika izveidots un verificēts izpētes viencilindra dīzeļmotora, aprīkota ar elektronisko apgriezienu regulatoru, dinamiskais matemātiskais modelis.

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